

A MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF FABRIC COMPOSITE MATERIAL LAMINAE

Yuan-chong ZHANG

Ying DAI *

(Research Institute of Engineering Mechanics,
Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, Shaanxi Province, P.R.CHINA)

ABSTRACT

A two-direction straight undulation model for plain weave composite is presented to evaluate elastic behaviour for plain weave composite laminae. Based on the two-direction model, the upper and lower bounds of the laminae elastic moduli are given by different constraint conditions applied on the top and bottom surfaces of the model in terms of the Classical Laminate Theory (CLT). A comparison of the resulting numerical predictions for weave composite laminae with some limited experimental data available shows that the two-direction undulation model is more valid for prediction of mechanical behaviour of plain weave composite laminae than one-direction model.

Keywords: plain weave composite, elastic constants, classical laminate theory.

* graduate student, Institute of Composite Mechanics and Structure, Tongji University, Shanghai, China.

1. INTRODUCTION

Practical applications of weave fabric composites are increasing in the area of advanced composite technology due to their more balanced properties in the fabric plane and better impact resistance than unidirectional laminae. Microdesign of the weave structure can provide great potential for improvement of the interlaminar and intralaminar strength and damage clearance of the fabric composite laminae. The ease of application and low fabrication cost have made fabric composites attractive for structural applications.

The prediction of effect of weave composite microstructure and constituents material properties on its macroscopic behaviour is one of the most important bases for optimum design. To the authors' knowledge, T.W.Chou and Ishikawa et al published some of papers treating the problem^[1,2], they proposed and developed a crimp model for approximating the elastic behaviour of woven fabric composites. In the model, the sinusoidal function form of the weft tows undulation is assumed only. Authors^[3,4] simplified the model and adopted a model with one-direction straight undulation instead. However, in substance these models are one-direction undulation ones and can not reflect both weft

and warp tows undulations in orthogonal directions, therefore there exists large discrepancy between the results of the theoretical predictions of transverse properties and experimental ones. To overcome the shortcomings, a two-direction straight undulation model for plain weave composite is presented to improve the results of the theoretical prediction. Based on the model, the classical laminate plate theory with out-of-plane deformation conditions, which was developed by Ishikawa [2], is adopted for the prediction of the upper and lower bounds of woven fabric laminae. A comparison of the numerical results with some limited experimental data available shows that the two-direction undulation model is more reasonable and valid than the one-direction models.

2. TWO-DIRECTION UNDULATION MODEL

The plain weave fabrics and the fabrics reinforced resin laminae are depicted in Fig.1-(a) and Fig.1-(b), which consists of weft tows, warp tows and pure resin matrix. The number of its repeating patterns of interlacing in orthogonal directions $n=2$. The geometric parameters of the straight undulation model a, a_u, h, h_t are symbolled in Fig.2(a). And it displays the feature of the fabric composite structure in weft tows direction. In Fig.2-(b), a representative volume element (RVE) of two-direction straight undulation model is given for the theoretical analysis model.

Figure 1. A plain weave fabric composite

Figure 2. Two-direction undulation model and its RVE

3. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

For plain weave fabric reinforced resin laminae shown in Fig.1-(b), the RVE (Fig.2-(b)) is adopted to study the variation of elastic constants with the ply number of the laminae. An arbitrary point (x,y) of the middle plane along the thickness direction of the RVE can be treated as a laminae consisting of pure resin layer, weft tows layer and warp tows layer, which have a variety of thickness.

It is assumed that the lamination theory is valid in an infinitesimal slice, therefore the local constitutive equations are written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_i \\ M_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{ij} & B_{ij} \\ B_{ij} & A_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_j^0 \\ k_j \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, 6$ and the directions of 1 and 2 coincide with those of the X and Y axes.

The local stiffness coefficients $A_{ij}(x, y)$, $B_{ij}(x, y)$ and $D_{ij}(x, y)$ can be easily calculated from

$$[A_{ij}(x, y), B_{ij}(x, y), D_{ij}(x, y)] = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (1, z, z^2) dz \quad (2)$$

where $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ is the k th-ply reduced stiffnesses after transformation to the natural coordinate system in $[h_{k-1}(x, y), h_k(x, y)]$ along the z axis.

The inverted form of equation (1) is written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^0 \\ k \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A' & B' \\ B'^T & D' \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $A' = A^{-1} + A^{-1}B(D - BA^{-1}B)BA^{-1}$

$$B' = -(A^{-1}B)(D - BA^{-1}B) \quad (4)$$

$$D' = (D - BA^{-1}B)$$

For a single layer of the weave fabric composite, due to the asymmetry of the distribution and properties of the constituent materials of the interlacing structure in the fabrics, the coupling stiffness matrix $B \neq 0$. Therefore, there exists the local coupling effect between in- and out-of-plane deformation. The macroscopic behaviour of fabric composites laminae is strongly governed by this effect. For example, the longitudinal modulus of weave fabric laminae increases with ply number. To evaluate the variation of the laminate properties with ply number, the upper and lower bounds of elastic constants of the laminae are given by combining local warping constrained and the opposing local warping allowed conditions applied at the bottom and top of the RVE shown in Fig.2-(b) with the classical laminate plate theory. The following two extreme conditions will be introduced.

1. Under the local warping constrained condition.

If any local warping is not allowed, the followed equations must hold:

$$\{k\} = 0, \quad \{M\} \neq 0 \quad (5)$$

From equation (3), the following equations are given:

$$\{\varepsilon^0\} = [A']\{N\} + [B']\{M\} \quad (6)$$

$$\{k\} = [B'^T]\{N\} + [D']\{M\} = 0 \quad (7)$$

From the equation (7), the following equation is obtained

$$\{M\} = -[D'^{-1}][B'^T]\{N\} \quad (8)$$

The substitution of equation (8) to equation (6) and

$$\{\varepsilon^0\} = \{[A'] - [B'] [D'^{-1}] [B'^T]\} \{N\} \quad (9)$$

Hence, macroscopic local in-plane compliance matrix $[a^*]$ is written as

$$[a^*] = [A'] - [B'] [D'^{-1}] [B'^T]$$

That is

$$[a^*] = A^{-1} \quad (10)$$

2. Under the local warping allowed condition.

If any local warping is allowed, the following equations must hold:

$$\{M\} = 0, \quad \{k\} \neq 0 \quad (11)$$

From equation (3), the following equation is obtained.

$$\{\varepsilon^0\} = A'\{N\} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, the corresponding macroscopic local in-plane compliance matrix is also written as

$$[a^{**}] = A' = A^{-1} + A^{-1}B(D - BA^{-1}B)BA^{-1} \quad (13)$$

The compliance matrix $[a^*]$ or $[a^{**}]$ is a function of coordinate (x, y) at the RVE. Hence the averaged in-plane compliance over the RVE can be calculated

$$[\bar{a}] = \frac{1}{ab} \int_{-\frac{a}{2}}^{\frac{a}{2}} \int_{-\frac{b}{2}}^{\frac{b}{2}} [a^*] \text{ or } [a^{**}] dx dy \quad (14)$$

The plane-stress anisotropic elastic stress-strain relation represented by engineering elastic constants is ^[5]

$$\{\varepsilon^0\} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{xx}} & -\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_{xx}} & \frac{\eta_{xy,x}}{E_{xx}} \\ -\frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_{yy}} & \frac{1}{E_{yy}} & \frac{\eta_{xy,y}}{E_{yy}} \\ \frac{\eta_{x,xy}}{G_{xy}} & \frac{\eta_{y,xy}}{G_{xy}} & \frac{1}{G_{xy}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where E_{xx} , E_{yy} are Young moduli along X and Y axes respectively, G_{xy} is shear modulus in xyplane, and ν_{xy} , ν_{yx} , Poisson Ratio; $\eta_{xy,x}$, $\eta_{xy,y}$, $\eta_{x,xy}$, $\eta_{y,xy}$ mutual influence coefficients.

By $N_x = h\sigma_x$, $N_y = h\sigma_y$, $N_{xy} = h\tau_{xy}$, the equation (15) is written as

$$\{\varepsilon^0\} = [a]\{N\} \quad (16)$$

where the compliance matrix is

$$[a] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{xx}h} & -\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_{xx}h} & \frac{\eta_{xy,x}}{E_{xx}h} \\ -\frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_{yy}h} & \frac{1}{E_{yy}h} & \frac{\eta_{xy,y}}{E_{yy}h} \\ \frac{\eta_{x,xy}}{G_{xy}h} & \frac{\eta_{y,xy}}{G_{xy}h} & \frac{1}{G_{xy}h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

By comparison of equations (17) with (14), it can be obtained $[a] = [\bar{a}]$ (18)

From the equation (18), the engineering elastic constants E , ν , G and η may be determined.

In general, the deformation state of every individual ply of the laminae is always between the preceding extreme situations 1 or 2, therefore the variation of the macroscopic behaviour of the laminae is expected to be between the two prediction values given by equation (14).

4. EXAMPLE AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

To evaluate the two-direction undulation model developed by the authors in the paper, a plain weave carbon / epoxy model shown in Fig.3. Its constituents material properties and geometry are taken from present experimental data [6]: $b = a$, $a = a_u = 2$ mm, $h = h_t = 0.2$ mm. The material properties are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Material Properties of Unidirectional tows and pure resin

Unidirectional CFRP					Pure resin	
E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	G_{LT} (GPa)	ν_{LT}	ν_{TT}	E_m (GPa)	ν_m
137.3	10.79	5.394	0.26	0.46	4.511	0.38

Figure 3. Two-direction model for plain weave carbon / epoxy composite
The material distribution of individual constituents along the Z axis is expressed as the weft tows layer:

$$h_2(x,y) < z < h_1(x,y) \quad y \in (-a/2, 0)$$

$$h_6(x,y) < z < h_5(x,y) \quad y \in (0, a/2)$$

The warp tows layer:

$$h_4(x,y) < z < h_7(x,y) \quad x \in (-a/2, 0)$$

$$h_8(x,y) < z < h_3(x,y) \quad x \in (a/2, 0)$$

The pure resin layer:

$$H(x,y) < z < h/2 \quad \text{or} \quad -h/2 < z < -H(x,y)$$

Where $h_i(x,y)$ ($i = 1, \dots, 8$) and $H(x,y)$ can be expressed as

$$h_1(x,y) = (x-y)\text{tg}\theta \quad h_2(x,y) = (x+y)\text{tg}\theta$$

$$h_5(x,y) = (-x+y)\text{tg}\theta \quad h_6(x,y) = -(x+y)\text{tg}\theta$$

$$h_3(x,y) = -(x+y)\text{tg}\theta \quad h_8(x,y) = (x-y)\text{tg}\theta$$

$$h_4(x,y) = (x+y)\text{tg}\theta \quad h_7(x,y) = (-x+y)\text{tg}\theta$$

$$H(x,y) = \begin{cases} h_3 & \text{when } x \in (-a/2, 0) \text{ and } y \in (-a/2, 0) \\ h_1 & \text{when } x \in (0, a/2) \text{ and } y \in (-a/2, 0) \\ h_5 & \text{when } x \in (-a/2, 0) \text{ and } y \in (0, a/2) \\ h_7 & \text{when } x \in (0, a/2) \text{ and } y \in (0, a/2) \end{cases}$$

$$\theta = \arctg(h_f / 2a_u) = \arctg(h / 2a)$$

To express true fibre tows volume fraction of a lamina, the coefficients k_m and k_f will be introduced and define

$$k_m = \frac{\text{True matrix volume fraction } V_m \text{ of the lamina}}{\text{matrix volume fraction of the RVE}} \quad (19)$$

$$k_f = \frac{\text{True fibre tows volume fraction } V_f \text{ of the lamina}}{\text{fibre tows volume fraction of the RVE}}$$

And then the reduced stiffnesses $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ in equations (2) are multiplied by k_f and k_m respectively. After the treatment, at first the stiffness matrices A, B and D of the model shown in Fig.3 can be calculated from (2) and obtain the compliance matrices $[a^*]$ and $[a^{**}]$ under the different extreme conditions, which are given by equations (10) and (13) respectively. Then the averaged compliance matrices $[\bar{a}^*]$ and $[\bar{a}^{**}]$ over the RVE may be obtained from (14) and by comparison to (17), the engineering elastic constants will be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{xx} &= 1 / h\bar{a}_{11} & E_{yy} &= 1 / h\bar{a}_{22} \\ \nu_{yx} &= -E_{xx} h\bar{a}_{12} & \nu_{xy} &= -E_{yy} h\bar{a}_{21} \\ \eta_{xy,x} &= E_{xx} h\bar{a}_{16} & \eta_{xy,y} &= E_{yy} h\bar{a}_{26} \\ G_{xy} &= 1 / h\bar{a}_{66} & \eta_{x,xy} &= G_{xy} h\bar{a}_{16} \\ \eta_{y,xy} &= G_{xy} h\bar{a}_{26} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The main numerical results for the model shown in Fig.3 are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Comparisons Between Theoretical Results of Two-type Models and Experiments

	E_{xx} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	E_{yy} (GPa)	ν_{yx}	G_{xy} (GPa)
Two-direction model LWC	64.97	0.0481	64.97	0.0481	5.45
LWA	37.91	0.0645	37.91	0.0645	5.45
One-direction model[4] LWC	71.12	0.0403	53.45	0.0615	4.82
LWA	53.04	0.0474	35.35	0.0562	4.82
Simple mixture rule *	56.66	----	-----	-----	----
single-ply Experiments[6]	48.3	0.062	48.3	0.062	5.41
8-ply	63.1	0.053	63.1	0.053	5.56
* Simple mixture rule $E = V_f E_f + V_w E_w + V_m E_m (V_f + V_w = 0.75, V_m = 0.25)$					

Also shown in Table 2 are the corresponding experimental and numerical results of the above-mentioned one-direction model. While a closer satisfactory upper and lower bounds of plain weave composite laminae are obtained from the two-direction undulation model with the CLT, experimental results can not included in those from the

one-direction model. Similar to result for one-direction model, the prediction of G_{xy} is independent of the two surfaces constraint conditions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Comparisons of the theoretical results of the two-direction model proposed by the authors with one-direction model ones and experiments lead to the following conclusions:

1. The plain weave composite with fibre tow undulations in orthogonal directions can be correctly modeled by the two-direction straight undulation model developed in the paper and the model possesses better symmetry for a balanced plain weave lamina than the one-direction one.

2. The theoretical results give a closer bounds of elastic behaviour of fabric composite laminae and the model is more reasonable and valid for theoretical prediction than preceding models.

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